

Composition of graminaceous and cyperaceous weed flora during a 2-year period at the plant virus experimental field, Kalyani, West Bengal, India.

Weed	Av no./m ²		Relative occurrence (%)	
	1976-77	1977-78	1976-77	1977-78
<i>Echinochloa colonum</i> (Graminae)	182	300	53.8	43.8
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> (Cyperaceae)	55	174	16.2	25.4
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (Graminae)	71	122	21.1	17.8
<i>Paspalum notavum</i> (Graminae)	30	58	8.8	8.5

kharif. The pots were used as virus sources in the field 35 to 40 days after inoculation. Twenty-five-day-old seedlings of TN1, Jaya, and Ratna were transplanted in replicated 1-m² plots prepared in random block design. One pot of inoculated *E. colonum* was placed

at the center of each plot. Each plot was then covered with nylon netting on wooden frames. Freshly emerged leafhoppers were released into each covered plot. The plants in each plot were observed until the booting stage. Ratna plants had 1.57% infection; Jaya,

6.4%; and TN1, 7.5%.

From this experiment it is apparent that the predominant graminaceous and cyperaceous weeds at the Kalyani virus experimental field do not contain any virus in natural conditions.

Weeds collected at Kalyani and other locations were inoculated with the virus. Only *E. colonum* and *P. notavum* were able to maintain the virus for 3 months.

In the field study with the inoculated *E. colonum* as the source plant, the virus was transmitted to all three test varieties (Ratna, Jaya, and TN1). Thus it is apparent that infected weeds such as *E. colonum* can act as the tungro virus source in the field. But no virus was detected in the weeds in natural conditions. Therefore, weeds may not play an important role in the field transmission of tungro. □

Occurrence of *Phaeotrichoconis crotalariae* on rice in Karnataka, India

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Many prerelease and released paddy cultures suffered from grain discoloration in 1977 kharif and 1978 summer in experimental plots at the Regional Research Station, VC Farm, Mandya, Karnataka. Derivatives of Basumathi and Sabarmati were particularly affected. When the discolored kernels were surface sterilized and incubated in moist chambers at room temperature (25-27°C), abundant spores of *Phaeotrichoconis crotalariae*, as well as the commonly known fungi involved in discoloration, were encountered. The fungus was easily isolated by the single-spore technique and pure-cultured on potato-dextrose agar. In the initial stages, the mycelial growth was whitish, but at maturity became dark grey. Conidia were produced after 4 days; sclerotia developed after 8 to 10 days. Descriptions of the fungus are similar to those provided by Subramanyam in 1956 and Vaidehi in 1971. Vaidehi had

isolated this fungus from TN1 rice kernels collected in 1967 in Andhra Pradesh, but the same fungus now occurs regularly and abundantly on many rice

varieties in Karnataka. This is the only information reported on its widespread occurrence on different rice varieties in Karnataka.

A rice disease observed by the late Bill Golden in Nepal

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After reading the article "Symptoms resembling those of rice dwarf disease in the Kathmandu Valley, Nepal" in the

IRRN 3(6):13-14, 1978, I found a color slide that was given to me by the late William (Bill) G. Golden, Jr., former IRRI rice production specialist and formerly with IRRI outreach programs in Sri Lanka and Bangladesh. The slide, taken by Bill in Kathmandu, Nepal, on 3 October 1966, shows A. N. Bhattarai

A photograph from a color slide taken by the late William G. Golden, Jr., in Kathmandu, Nepal, in 1966 showing A. N. Bhattarai holding a rice hill with symptoms similar to those of rice dwarf disease described in Japan.

holding a rice hill with symptoms similar to those of rice dwarf disease described in Japan: 1) stunting of plants, 2) profuse tillering, and 3) appearance of yellowish white specks forming

interrupted streaks on leaf blades. The streaks are parallel to the midribs.

I recall having told Bill that the symptoms were similar to those of rice dwarf disease but that we needed

transmission results, virus properties, etc. to make that conclusion. Therefore, the information was not published. □

Effect of transplanting time on the spread of tungro in boro

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An experiment at the plant virus experimental field studied the effect of transplanting time on the spread of tungro virus disease in rice during the 1977–78 boro. The Indian Council of

Agricultural Research, New Delhi, funded the research

TN1 seedlings at 25 days of age were transplanted at 5-day intervals in replicated plots, 3 m² each. Each plot was provided with uniform inoculum for tungro virus (1 infected plant/plot). The number of plants with tungro symptoms at the booting stage was recorded.

Transplanting time appears to have pronounced effects on the spread of

tungro (see table). The disease spread among seedlings that were transplanted in December, but not among those transplanted in January. The percentage of infection was high in seedlings transplanted in mid-December, then gradually declined toward the end of the month. Thus, early transplanting in boro may encourage tungro, maybe because tungro vectors are present in the field only until late December and are absent during January. □

Effect of transplanting time of TN1 seedlings on the spread of rice tungro virus disease during the boro season (Dec.–Mar.) and the corresponding vector population in the field. West Bengal, India.

Transplanting date	Vector population/sweep ^a												Plants infected with tungro (%)
	20 Dec 1977	25 Dec	2 Jan 1978	9 Jan	15 Jan	22 Jan	29 Jan	7 Feb	15 Feb	30 Feb	7 Mar	16 Mar	
15 Dec 1977	5	4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	3	3	80
20 Dec	4	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	60
25 Dec		2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	3	30
30 Dec			1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	5
4 Jan 1978				0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0
9 Jan				0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	2	0
14 Jan					0	0	0	0	0	2	0	1	0

^a3-m² plots.

Effects of foliar spray of micronutrients on rice sheath blight disease

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Plants of the susceptible rice variety ADT31 at the maximum-tillering stage were inoculated with the *Rhizoctonia solani* pathogen, which causes sheath blight disease. The field trial had a randomized block design with four replications during the 1975 kuruvai (June–Sept.) and the 1975–76 thaladi (Oct.–Jan.). Two foliar sprays of the micronutrients borax, ammonium molybdate, zinc sulfate, magnesium sulfate, calcium sulfate, copper sulfate,

and ferrous sulfate were applied twice at 0.059% level at 10-day intervals.

Disease intensity was then assessed. All the micronutrients reduced the disease and increased the grain yield in both seasons. The effects were mal-ked with borax, zinc sulfate, copper sulfate, and ferrous sulfate. □

Effects of fungicidal spray on the population of *R. solani* and on rhizospheric microflora of rice

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ADT31, which is susceptible to the sheath blight disease caused by

Rhizoctonia solani, was raised in pots and inoculated with the pathogen. The seedlings were sprayed with a 0.025% solution of the fungicides Brassicol, wettable cerasan, Thiabendazole, Benlate, Vitavax, Bavistin, Kitazin, Demosan, Daconil, and Hinosan at 20, 25, and 30 days after sowing. The populations of fungi, bacteria, actinomycetes, and *R. solani* in rhizospheric and nonrhizospheric soils were estimated 48 hours later. Fungicidal spray drastically reduced the rhizospheric population of *R. solani*. Foliar sprays of Kitazin, Hinosan, Benlate, Vitavax, and Bavistin reduced the pathogen in the rhizosphere more than the other fungicides did. The fungicidal sprays stimulated the bacterial and actinomycetal populations considerably, but inhibited the fungal populations.